

Tautology and Contradiction with the Speech of Iraqi (EFL) 6th Class Students

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: August 27, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: March 30, 2022</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : EFL Iraqi learners, Tautology, Contradiction, Students</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6464009</p>	<p><i>The current study is concerned with "Tautology and Contradiction" which are considered as two types of proposition in relation to semantics. The problem of this study is that EFL Iraqi learners face certain difficulties in their own speech, that is, it sometimes contains certain words or expressions that have the same meaning, i.e., tautology, on one hand. On the other hand, learners sometimes use false propositions in terms of speech, i.e. contradiction. The study also aims at re-establishing the concepts of "tautology and contradiction in addition to measure EFL Iraqi learners' speech whether it involves "tautology and contradiction". It is hypothesized that there is, unfortunately, wrong usage of words or expressions due to the translation from Arabic to English. Furthermore, "tautology and contradiction" may be caused by transmitting certain ideas from the mother tongue. To achieve its aims and verify its hypotheses, the study adopts the following steps:</i></p> <p>(i) <i>Describing the notions of "tautology and contradiction".</i> (ii) <i>Presenting the essential kinds of "tautology" in terms of semantics.</i> (iii) <i>Following Lyons (1995)' model.</i> (iv) <i>Coming out with a number of conclusions.</i></p> <p><i>Concerning the data analysis, it is limited to (20) EFL Iraqi learners who have undergone the test in the present study that are 6th class students of Sifeen School for boys for the academic year 2021-2022. The result is that learners fail to employ accurate propositions through their speech.</i></p>

Introduction

Lyons (1995: 151-152) mentions that "tautology and contradiction" can be classified as being lexically anomalous. In terms of face-value, they are uninformative, that is, they cannot be utilized to tell someone issues that they did not know earlier or could not conclude themselves on the ground of their awareness of the language and the capacity to draw adequate inferences from what they previously know. Whatever lexically anomalous or meaningless denotes in relation to contradictions and tautologies, it cannot indicate "devoid of sense". Tautology and contradiction are by definition essentially true and essentially false respectively implying that a contradictory sentence should have determinable truth-condition. Thus, the former are true and the latter are false in all possible worlds.

Tautologies and contradictions have long been believed to be accurate understood. Tautology have been much investigated in the literature, particularly regarding the question of whether to explained nominal tautologies, like "*Boys will be boys*", (Wierzbicka, 1988: 225). None supply a unified investigation which captures the usages of different aspects of tautologies by virtue of a single mechanism. Contradiction has also got some attention (Alxatib, et al, 2013: 620), though there too solely some of the related phenomena have been addressed.

1.2 Literature Review

In this section, it will be explained the terms of "tautology and contradiction" in details.

1.2.1 Concept of Tautology

Tautology refers to a function of context, for such reason, States (2000: 51-66) maintains that "depending on where you choose to stand on the scales of sameness and difference and pertness and wholeness, you could as well argue that there is no such thing as tautology or that the whole world itself is a tautology." Besides, Saeed (2016: 454) elaborates that in logic, statements cannot be refuted without contradictions. It is true under any comprehension. In this respect, Kearns (2010: 11) describes tautology as "a statement which is always true and cannot be false", as in:

a. "*When Jones was walking his feet moved*".

b. "*The universe is either expanding or not expanding*".

When different expressions are utilized to deliver the same sense, it is suggested that senses of such expressions are exceeding the expressive powers of the concerned words, (Keach, 2004: 27-35). For Traugott (1980:206):

- **Evoking idealized stereotype/ extreme example**

Tautologies can be employed to trigger most examples that can be seen as an idealized stereotype. This function can be represented as: 'subordinate conjunction' and 'equative'.

1.3 Contradiction: Definitions

Broadly speaking, Maritain (2003: 133) classifies logical opposition into three basic kinds: *contradiction*, *contrariety* and *sub-contrariety*. Thus, the concept contradiction is regarded as one basic type of logical opposition. Thus, a statement A is regarded as a contradiction of B if A and B cannot both be considered true in any conditions. If the contradictory sentences A and B are connected in a complex sentence D, so D is also known a contradiction. For instance:

- 8 a. "Jones is at home" contradicts "Jones is not at home", and vice versa".
- b. "This clock is fast and slow".

A contradiction cannot be true because solely one part or the other can be true in a given condition, (Kearns, 2010: 11). It can also be described contradiction as a type of semantic relations between sentences. It exists when sentences are unlikely being correct at the same time. For instance, the contradiction occurs between the sentence pairs "Some people and vehicles are on a crowded street" and "Some people and vehicles are on an empty street", (De Marneffe, et al., 2008: 1039).

According to Miller and Brown (2013: 108), contradiction indicates two propositions that are contradictory if they cannot both be true or false. In other words, one contradicts the other, e.g. of the propositions: "The boy broke the window and the boy didn't break the window", one must be true and the other one false (The boy points out the same person and the window to the identical window). They (ibid) add that contradictory propositions may contain complementaries, such as, "dead" and "alive" or reversives such as, "up" and "down". Of the propositions: "The plants are dead and the plants are alive", one should be true and the other false. Similarly: "The lift is going up and the lift is going down", assuming that "the lift is moving".

Consequently, Allan (2009: 26) illustrates that contradiction relations occur between the negation or assertion of one individual of the set and the disjunction of the others. For example, "X is an animal" contradicts "X is a vegetable or a mineral", and "X is not an animal" entails "X is a vegetable or a mineral". In this respect, Crystal (2011: 111) points out that contradiction is a sentence that cannot be true, by means of its meaning and form. For instance, "This table is more than 10 feet long, but it is less than 10 feet long".

For Fromkin et al. (2014), contradiction is utilized to describe a sentence that is false based on its meaning alone, irrespective of context: e.g., "Kings are female". They (ibid) add that speakers' consciousness of sentence meaning involves:

"knowing the truth condition of declarative sentences; that is, knowing when a sentence entails another e; knowing when two sentences are paraphrases or contradictory; knowing when a sentence is a tautology, contradiction, or paradox; and knowing when sentences are ambiguous, among other things. Compositional semantics is the building up of phrasal or sentence meaning from the meaning of smaller units by means of semantic rules".

Finally, Murphy and Koskela (2010: 47) concludes that one sense of contradiction is a kind of propositional relations. A proposition P conflicts another Q if and only "if the truth of P entails the falsity of Q". For instance, any sentence regards as contradicted one by its negation:

9. "Jean ate snails contradicts Jean did not eat snails".

Some propositions including antonyms are regarded as contradictions:

10. "Elvis is alive contradicts Elvis is dead".
11. "Elvis died in 1977 contradicts Elvis was alive in 1980".

Contradiction can also point out a property of a proposition. In this case, contradictory propositions cannot be true. For instance, "Hughie was dead when he was alive" is a contradiction if one takes 'dead' and 'alive' in their literal senses, (ibid).

2.1 Methodology

The present section is concerned with the practical steps that are explained the procedures to measure the level of learners' difficulties of the concerned issues. Nevertheless, Lyons (1995)'s model will be adopted in the present study.

2.2 Description Test

The test is basically depended on the production one. The EFL Iraqi learners are needed to state meaningful sentences following the academic strategies.

2.3 The Population

The EFL Iraqi learners who have subjected the test in the current study are Sifeen School for boys. The sample is about (20) learners, for the academic year 2021-2022. They are in the same age as well as they are non-native speakers. This sample is elected since they consider master a suitable number of lexemes due to their expending enough time in learning English. Furthermore, each learner should answer the two concerned questions (See appendix B).

2.4 Instrument

The method adopted in this study is a quantitative in nature. Williams (2011: 14) states that the concerned method refers to measure and analyze variables to reach particular findings. The quantitative method involves analyzing and utilizing numeral data in terms of utilizing certain statistical procedure to reach particular answers to the concerned tests.

2.5 Validity and Reliability

For the purpose of making the study too more appropriately designed and consistent, it is useful to achieve the two essential preconditions of validity and reliability. For validity of a test, Heaton (1974: 78) affirms that it is the scope to which it measures what it is assumed measuring and nothing else. Tests must be as valid as their lecturers make them. The test should attempt to provide true measures of the certain skill that it is aimed to measure. As far as reliability is concerned, it have to do with constancy of marks for the common learners. If their marks are constant, the test will be credible; if they tend to tumble with no obvious reasons, it will not be credible, (Harmer, 2001: 90).

2.6 Final Administration

The last version of the tests was carried out by employing online educational program, such as, Telegram on 3 of November 2021 on (20) learners elected randomly from the Sifeen School for boys for the academic year 2021-2022. The EFL Iraqi students took only (45) minutes to provide their meaningful sentences. Moreover, they have been inform not to write down their names for the purpose of avoid possible embarrassments. Some answers of learners are attached (See appendix A).

2.7 Analysis of Data and Discussion

After subjecting learners to the test, the researcher got the results as presented in the following tables:

Table (1) Frequency of "Tautology" for the First Question

NO. of Students	Sentences with Tautology	Sentences without Tautology
1	7	3
2	4	6
3	6	4
4	4	6
5	7	3
6	2	8
7	6	4
8	9	1
9	5	5
10	3	7
11	5	5
12	5	5
13	7	3
14	6	4
15	3	7
16	8	2
17	9	1
18	10	0
19	7	3
20	6	4
Total	119	81
Percentages	59%	41%

Table (2) Frequency of "Contradiction" for the Second Question

NO. of Students	Sentences with Contradiction	Sentences without Contradiction
1	1	5
2	1	5
3	1	5
4	1	4
5	0	5
6	2	3
7	1	4
8	2	3
9	0	5
10	2	3
11	2	3
12	2	3
13	0	5
14	0	5
15	3	2
16	2	1
17	0	5
18	0	5
19	2	3
20	2	2
Total	24	76
Percentages	13%	87%

From the above tables, it has been shown that the number of sentences with tautology, in table (1), are (119) which rates (59%). This percentage is higher than the number of sentences without tautology which are (81) that scores (41%). As for table (2), the number of sentences with contradiction are (27) which rates (13%). Such percentage is lower than the number of sentences without contradiction which are (73) that scores (87%).

2.8 Results

It has been noticed that EFL Iraqi learners have no ability to answer the concerned questions that are stated by the lecturer. Their findings show that they do not have adequate knowledge towards "tautology and contradiction". This result may belong to particular reasons. One of the most important reasons is that EFL Iraqi learners do not interpret the concepts in question. They do not highlight on lexemes of English language, as a foreign language, where some learners confuse between their first language and the concerned language. Secondly, some lecturers may follow classical approaches through teaching the semantic relations. It has been suggested that students must be more careful towards their own curriculums. Besides, lecturers have also to follow technological methods in order to improve the scientific level of Iraqi learners in addition to emphasize better references, for instances, Lyons (1995) and Saeed (2016).

Conclusion

The following points are concluded:

1. Tautology points out expressions which are "true by definition", showing no novel information, such as: "*A gander is a male goose* or *Word endings come at the end of words*".
2. To distinguish the functions of tautologies, Wierzbicka's (1987) typology is proposed in this study as observed in the following types: "acceptance/ Resignation, denial of difference within category, distinctness of categories, obligation, highlighting wysiwyg nature and evoking idealized stereotype/ extreme example.
3. Contradiction indicates two propositions that are contradictory if they cannot both be true or false.

4. As far as the practical side of the study, the concerned students do not have adequate knowledge towards "tautology and contradiction". Thus, the hypothesis of the present study is verified.

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